

Energy Transition Pathways for Zambia: A Modelling Approach Using OseMOSYS

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Executive Summary

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of Zambia's energy future, focusing on three scenarios: Business as Usual (BAU), Government Renewable Energy Policy (REW), and Drought Impact Scenario (DIS). The key findings reveal that the BAU scenario, which heavily relies on hydropower, presents significant risks in terms of vulnerability to climate change with high emissions of about 2000 kt CO₂ compared to REW and DIS whose emission contribution is slightly about 1650 kt CO₂ through the modelling period. Despite the high initial investment cost in the installation capacity of more than 10000 millions USD and 13000 millions USD respectively for REW and DIS scenarios. The results demonstrate an increase in installation capacity of variable renewable energy sources like solar PV and wind in diversification of the energy mix in the REW and DIS which significantly enhance the resilience and sustainability of Zambia's energy system.

Recommendations: To secure a sustainable energy future, Zambia should prioritise the following actionable steps:

1. **Expand Renewable Energy Integration:** Implement policies that facilitate the growth of solar PV and wind capacity, aiming to meet or exceed the 30% renewable energy target by 2030.
2. **Develop Energy Storage Solutions:** Introduce incentives for the development and deployment of energy storage technologies to support renewable integration.
3. **Enhance Climate Resilience:** Incorporate climate risk assessments into energy planning to mitigate the impact of droughts and other climate-related disruptions.

These recommendations will guide Zambia toward a more secure, sustainable, and resilient energy future.

1.0 Introduction

Zambia's energy sector generation mix is characterised by a heavy reliance on hydropower, as of 31st December 2023 the total national installed capacity was about 3800 MW which constitutes over 83% of hydropower, 3.2% solar, 8.7% coal, 2.9% HFO and diesel 2.2%. This dependency on hydropower coupled with the impacts of climate change, has led to increasing energy insecurity, with frequent droughts causing significant disruptions in power supply to meet national electricity demand of about 2400 MW (Konkell & Young, 2020). Additionally, Zambia faces substantial challenges in extending access to electricity meeting its demand especially for peri-urban and rural areas while adhering to its international climate commitments. Approximately the overall average electricity access rate is about 45% and average electricity access rate in rural areas is only 8% (World Bank, 2020).

Against this background, the Government of the Republic of Zambia has set ambitious targets to diversify its energy mix and aspires to become a middle-income economy by 2030 (National Energy Policy, 2019). While the nation faces the challenge of reducing its dependency on hydropower, it also has the potential to harness abundant renewable energy resources, such as solar and wind, to build a more resilient energy future. To support this, a key national target has been set to achieve 30% of its electricity production from variable renewable energy sources by 2030.

To navigate this complex broader strategy of energy generation mix, and promote sustainable development, an Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OseMOSYS) widely recognized for long-term energy planning was used to explore and evaluate three different scenarios for Zambia's energy transition pathways namely; (i) Business-As-Usual (BAU) (ii) Government Renewable Energy Policy (RE Policy), (iii) Drought Impact (DIS). The flexibility and transparency of OseMOSYS make it particularly well-suited for assessing the dynamics of Zambia's energy system and identifying optimal strategies for achieving a sustainable, reliable, and cost-effective energy mix.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this work was to conduct a comprehensive analysis of Zambia's current energy system, with a particular focus on exploring potential pathways for energy transition in the power sector. The scope of the study was restricted to modelling various three scenarios over a long-term horizon up to 2070, considering factors such as variable renewable integration, technological advancements and energy policy interventions.

1.2 Objective and aim

To model different energy scenarios for Zambia to assess the potential impacts of integrating variable renewable energy sources in the generation mix. Its main aim of study was to identify and evaluate optimal energy transition pathways for Zambia that support the development of a sustainable, resilient, and cost-effective energy system by modelling three different scenarios.

2.0 Methodology

This study leverages on the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OseMOSYS) as a primary tool for modelling different energy scenarios (Howells, et al., 2011). In addition, an Advanced Energy System Modelling Using OseMOSYS for Model Calibration of primary energy and power sector using clicSAND (Plazas-Niño F., 2024). To ensure accuracy and reliability of data used in the modelling, a range of authorities were reviewed such as; National Energy Balance Reports from the Ministry of Energy, Zambia, ZESCO Limited 2021-2031 Strategic Plan. Renewable Energy Resource Assessments conducted by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), Socio-economic Data from the Central Statistical Office of Zambia, Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) by the Ministry of Energy 2024, Energy Sector Report by the Energy Regulation Board (ERB) 2023

Modelling assumptions considered were as follows:

- Energy Demand Projections: This was projected based on historical consumption patterns, anticipated population growth, and sectoral economic development trends outlined in the 8th National Development Plan.
- Technology Costs and Performance: The costs and performance metrics for energy technologies, including hydropower, solar, wind, and biomass, was derived from the most recent national and international datasets (IRENA, 2020)
- Policy Scenarios and Environmental Considerations: The model incorporated the impact of Zambia's energy policy, which mandates that 30% of electricity generation from variable renewable energy sources (VRES) by 2030.

The three scenarios were developed to address specific aspects of Zambia's energy system:

- Business as Usual (BAU) Scenario: This scenario assumes the continuation of current policies and trends without significant changes in the energy mix or policy interventions. The BAU scenario serves as a baseline, enabling comparison with more proactive policy-driven scenarios.
- Government Renewable Energy Policy (REW) scenario: This scenario models the impact of Zambia's policy goal to achieve 30% of its electricity production from solar and wind by 2030. It explores the potential shifts in the energy mix, reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, and the cost investments of integrating large-scale VRES.
- Drought Impact Scenario (DIS): This scenario models the impact of a cyclic drought period, with droughts assumed to occur every 5 years starting with 2024. The scenario focuses on the implications of these recurrent droughts and other climate variability on Zambia's hydropower-dominated energy system.

3.0 Results

In this section present the key findings from the energy system modelling for Zambia, focusing on the three scenarios: Business as Usual (BAU), Government Renewable Energy Policy (REW), and Drought Impact Scenario (DIS). The analysis focused on critical aspects such as generation capacity, installed capacity, investment costs, and emissions. The results are illustrated through a series of charts and graphs to highlight the main outcomes, compare the differences between scenarios, and provide insights into the implications for Zambia’s energy strategy.

Figure 1: Installed Capacity

The trends in installed capacity, depicted in Figure 1, highlight the differences in strategic energy planning across the scenarios. The BAU scenario is primarily driven by large hydropower projects, with installed capacity reaching approximately 10 GW by 2070. However, it can be seen that the REW scenario shows a higher installed capacity, reaching 11 GW in 2070. This increase is mainly due to the deployment of renewable energy technologies such as solar PV and wind energy. In addition, the DIS scenario maintains a balanced growth, reaching about 12 GW, with significant contributions from off-grid hydropower and renewables, designed to mitigate the effects of cyclic droughts.

Figure 2: Power Generation, units in PJ

As shown in Figure 2, the BAU scenario heavily relies on large hydropower, which increases steadily from 2015 to 2070. The total power generation peaks at approximately 160 PJ by 2070, indicating a continued dependency on hydropower. In contrast, results illustrate that the REW scenario significantly diversifies the energy mix, incorporating substantial contributions from solar PV and wind, which reduces reliance on a single energy source and promotes a more balanced power generation portfolio.

Figure 3: Investment Costs

Investment costs across the scenarios vary significantly, as shown in Figure 3. The BAU scenario shows relatively high investment costs, especially post-2040, primarily due to the expansion of large hydropower capacity. The REW scenario, however, displays a more balanced cost distribution, with initial higher investments in solar PV and wind stabilising over time. The

DIS scenario, on the other hand, shows moderate investment costs, with strategic allocations aimed at enhancing resilience against climate variability.

Figure 4: Emissions

The environmental impact of each scenario is starkly illustrated in Figure 4. The BAU scenario results in the highest emissions. Figure 4 also shows that emissions in the REW scenario remain low and stable throughout the period, highlighting the effectiveness of integrating renewables in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Similarly, the DIS scenario maintains low emissions, despite the challenges posed by cyclic droughts, thanks to the strategic shift towards renewable energy sources.

4. Discussion

The results of this study offer critical insights into Zambia's future energy landscape, highlighting the implications of different energy strategies and the associated trade-offs. By examining the Business as Usual (BAU), Government Renewable Energy Policy (REW), and Drought Impact Scenario (DIS), the report provides a comprehensive understanding of how each approach could shape the country's energy security, economic development, and environmental sustainability.

The findings underscore the importance of diversification in Zambia's energy mix. The REW scenario demonstrates that by strategically integrating renewable energy sources, particularly solar PV and wind, Zambia can significantly reduce its greenhouse gas emissions, stabilise investment costs, and ensure a more resilient power generation system. This scenario aligns with global trends toward decarbonization and supports Zambia's commitment to mitigating climate change.

The DIS scenario further emphasises the need for resilience in the face of climate variability. As Zambia continues to rely heavily on hydropower, the potential for drought-induced disruptions remains a critical concern. Diversifying energy sources, including off-grid solutions and increased reliance on renewables, presents a viable pathway to mitigate these risks. This scenario highlights the dual benefits of improving energy security while maintaining low emissions.

In contrast, the BAU scenario, while reflecting the current trajectory, presents significant risks. The continued reliance on large hydropower projects, without substantial investment in alternative energy technologies, leads to higher emissions, increased long-term investment costs, and greater vulnerability to climate impacts. This scenario serves as a cautionary tale, illustrating the potential pitfalls of maintaining the status quo without proactive policy interventions.

5.0 Policy and Technological Recommendations

5.1 Policy Recommendations

Given the insights gained from results we recommend the following:

- i. **Prioritise Renewable Energy Integration:** The Zambian government should continue to prioritise the integration of renewable energy into the national grid. Policies that support investments in solar PV, wind, and off-grid solutions will be crucial for achieving energy security and sustainability goals.
- ii. **Incentivize Energy Storage Development:** Developing and deploying energy storage technologies should be a key focus of future energy policy. Incentives for private sector investment in energy storage could accelerate the adoption of these technologies.

- iii. **Strengthen Climate Resilience in Energy Planning:** Energy policies should incorporate climate risk assessments and resilience strategies, particularly in relation to hydropower. Diversifying the energy mix is essential to safeguarding Zambia's energy system against the impacts of climate variability.

5.2 Technological Recommendations

- i. **Solar PV and Onshore Wind:** The success of the REW scenario suggests that further investment in solar and wind technologies could be instrumental in achieving Zambia's energy goals. These technologies offer scalable and relatively low-cost solutions for diversifying the energy mix and reducing emissions.
- ii. **Off-grid and Mini-grid Solutions:** Particularly relevant in the DIS scenario, off-grid and mini-grid systems powered by renewables can play a crucial role in enhancing energy access in remote areas. These systems are not only resilient to climate impacts but also crucial for addressing the rural-urban disparity in energy access.
- iii. **Energy Storage Technologies:** To complement the integration of intermittent renewable sources like solar and wind, energy storage technologies such as batteries and pumped hydro storage could be critical. These technologies help stabilise the grid, manage peak loads, and ensure a reliable power supply even when renewable generation is low.

5.3 Limitations of the study and future research

Despite the comprehensive nature of this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. The first challenge raised from data constraints. The accuracy of the model outputs depends on the quality and availability of data. In cases where data was limited or outdated, assumptions had to be made, which could affect the precision of the results. The study assumes continued cost reductions and performance improvements in renewable energy technologies. However, these assumptions may not fully capture potential future technological or market disruptions. In addition, the Simplified Climate Impact Modelling approach may lack capturing all climate related challenges. While the DIS scenario incorporates drought impacts, the study does not fully account for other climate-related risks, such as extreme weather events, which could also affect the energy system. These limitations open door to potential research areas which need further exploration:

- i. **Expanded Climate Risk Assessments:** Future studies could incorporate a wider range of climate risks, including extreme weather events, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the potential impacts on Zambia's energy system.
- ii. **Detailed Economic Analysis of Energy Storage:** While this study highlights the importance of energy storage, further research is needed to assess the economic feasibility and potential market mechanisms for deploying storage technologies at scale.

- iii. Exploration of Decentralised Energy Systems: Further research into decentralised energy systems, including microgrids and community-based energy initiatives, could provide valuable insights into how these systems could enhance energy access and resilience.

Policy Implementation Challenges: Finally, exploring the challenges of implementing the recommended policies, particularly in terms of regulatory, financial, and institutional barriers, would be crucial for translating research into action.

6.0 Conclusion

This study highlights the critical importance of diversifying Zambia's energy mix to ensure a sustainable and resilient energy future. The analysis across the three scenarios—Business as Usual (BAU), Government Renewable Energy Policy (REW), and Drought Impact Scenario (DIS)—demonstrates that reliance on a single energy source, particularly hydropower, poses significant risks, especially in the context of climate variability. The results in the three scenarios shows an increase in installation capacity of above 10 GW for both in REW and DIS as compared to the BAU of about 9 GW in capacity. In terms of generation, the finding shows the total power generation peaks at approximately 160 PJ by 2070, indicating a continued dependency on hydropower. The carbon emission and investment cost in three scenarios shows continued increase in emission in BAU about 2000 kt CO₂ compared to REW and DIS whose emission contribution is slightly about 1650 kt CO₂. In terms of investment, the results show more investment cost REW and DIS of more 10 000 million USD to mitigate the carbon emission.

Key lessons learned include the necessity of integrating renewable energy sources such as solar PV and wind, which not only reduce emissions but also stabilise investment costs and enhance energy security. The study also underscores the value of developing energy storage solutions and off-grid systems to address both climate resilience and energy access challenges.

Zambia should prioritise the adoption of policies that support the expansion of renewable energy, incentivize energy storage technologies, and integrate climate risk assessments into energy planning. These steps will be crucial in achieving a balanced, sustainable, and resilient energy system that can meet the country's future needs while minimising environmental impact. The study provides a roadmap for Zambia's energy future, emphasising the need for proactive policy interventions, technological innovation, and climate resilience to ensure a sustainable and secure energy system.

References

- Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., Heaps, C., Huntington, H., Kypreos, S., & Loulou, R. (2011). OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System: An introduction to its ethos, structure, and development. *Energy Policy*, 5850-5870.
- International Energy Agency. (2019). *Africa Energy Outlook 2019*. Paris: IEA.
- Konkell, D., & Young, J. (2020). Hydropower and Climate Change in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Focus on Zambia. *Journal of Energy Research*, 105-120.
- World Bank. (2020). Access to Electricity (% of population) - Zambia. Retrieved from World Bank Group: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EG.ELC.ACCS.ZS?locations=ZM>
- Zambia Ministry of Energy. (2021). *Renewable Energy Policy 2021*. Lusaka: Government of Zambia.
- Plazas-Niño, F. (2024, July). *Advanced Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS: Model Calibration*
– Primary energy (Version 2.0).
- Cannone, C., Allington, L., De Wet, N., Shivakumar, A., Goyns, P., Valderrama, C., Kell A., PlazasNiño, F., Mohanty, R., Kapur, V., Wright, J., Yeganyan, R., Tan, N., Seng To, L., Harrison, J., Howells, M. (2023). clicSAND [computer software]. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1338761/v3>
- Plazas-Niño, F. (2024, July). *Advanced Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS: Model Calibration*
– Power Sector (Version 2.0).
- Martindale, L., & Cannone, C. (2023, January 18). *Formulating Scenario(s) for your Country with clicSAND Interface*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7548105>